

IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON HOUSEHOLD SAVINGS BEHAVIOR IN COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT: The study aims to understand the evolving relationship between socioeconomic variables and household savings patterns in Coimbatore. The study sets three research objectives that are crucial for the study's achievement. The major points of discussion are; how household income levels affect savings behaviors, how education is connected with household savings, and the employment relationship with savings distribution across investments. The study explores education, income, employment, etc involving various demographic backgrounds to understand the socioeconomic status of the savings behavior. The data was collected from the Coimbatore district, having the specialty of a group of diverse people. The study aims to statistically evaluate the data to give a clear picture of the actual scenario through validation by applying statistical models. The statistical tools relevant to the situation based on the assumptions will provide a clear understanding of the savings patterns of Coimbatore households. The study has both theoretical and practical implications. The major findings of the study are; that the majority of the respondents completed secondary-level education, most of the respondents are employed full-time and the majority of the respondents earn 20,001-40,000 monthly as their total household income, there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income, there is a substantial difference in all variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save, and the most preferred variable in the allocation of savings among different investment avenues is stock market investments. The result shows that there is a difference in the preference for the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The study has both theoretical and practical implications.

Keywords: Household, savings, savings behavior, socioeconomic factors, Coimbatore

INTRODUCTION

Household savings anywhere is the core element for the ability to maintain economic growth and financial stability (Bhatia and Tyagi, 2018). The role was to satisfy and achieving long-term and short-term financial objectives such as “homeownership and retirement”, “investments in health”,

and “investments in education” (Vadde, 2015; Kumarasinghe and Jayasinghe, 2016; Saqib et al., 2016; Bashir, 2011). The saving habit for meeting uncertainties in the future is also the nature of financial sustainability by the households (Kozera et al., 2016). According to Anvari-Clark and Ansong, 2022, “comprehending the variables that impact the savings habits of households is crucial in formulating policies that foster economic expansion and financial stability” (Anvari-Clark and Ansong, 2022). Coimbatore is a city in the Tamil Nadu state in India having diverse socio-economic status and the natural households who are highly saving in their income. The study was mainly conducted in this specific region. The city is considered an industrial region and well-established information technology industry (Ismail and Rashid, 2013; Maftuhin and Kusumawardani, 2022; Gedela, 2012). The diversified population including employed both full-time and part-time, self-employed especially entrepreneurs and gig workers, with various levels of income, educational qualification, cultural status, values, norms, etc. is the major highlight of the city which turns the theme into most suitable for the research. Cvetkovic and Sisovic, 2024, highlighted that “households manage and distribute their financial resources can be greatly impacted by the interaction of multiple socio-economic factors, including income levels, education, employment status, and cultural norms (Cvetkovic and Sisovic, 2024; Loko et al., 2013; Njung’e, 2013; Gerhard et al., 2018; Derevyankina, 2021).

The saving habit is significant and good practice, but it is a very difficult task. The cost of living is another constraint experienced by the households in the Coimbatore region. The cost is mainly incurred in the form of living, health, education, transportation, etc (Hill and Webber, 2022; Brounen et al., 2016; Faridi and Bashir, 2010) which hinders the future savings of money and their surplus income. Graham et al., 2024; Cliff et al., 2023 defined and identified that “demographic groups may have varied saving habits as a result of socioeconomic differences within a particular city” (Graham et al., 2024; Cliff et al., 2023). The diversity is important for treatments fostering financial resilience of every household (Infurna et al., 2020).

An association exists between socioeconomic characteristics and savings behavior. It is evident in the existing literature. There is an existing research gap in the literature on this field especially focused on Coimbatore. This examination of the socio-economic status will fill the gap evolved. By examining the demographic characteristics, the study will help to identify the opportunities, challenges, and factors of the savings behavior of households in the Coimbatore region which is essential for financial growth and stability.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study aims to understand the evolving relationship between the socio-economic variables and household savings patterns in Coimbatore. The study sets three research objectives that are crucial for the study's achievement. The major points of discussion are; how household income levels affect savings behaviors, how education is connected with household savings, and also the employment relationship with savings distribution across investments. The study explores education, income, employment, etc involving various demographic backgrounds to understand the socioeconomic status of the savings behavior. The data was collected from the Coimbatore district, having a specialty of a group of diversified people. The study aims to statistically evaluate the data to give a clear picture of the actual scenario through validation by applying statistical models. The statistical tools which relevant to the situation based on the assumptions will provide a clear understanding of the savings patterns of Coimbatore households. The study has both theoretical and practical implications.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is significant due to the filling of existing research gaps in the literature through an empirical analysis. The socio-economic background is influencing the savings patterns which are impacting the future. The importance of understanding these patterns has a role in formulating economic policies and financial planning on an individual society, and international level. The relationship between education, income, employment, etc involving various demographic backgrounds is another significant highlight of this study. The study is also significant due to the following examinations as determination of the influence of income levels on household savings habits, the investigation of the relationship between education levels' propensity to save among households, and the analysis of the effect of employment status on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The implications of the study both theoretical and practical are another sig

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The statement of the problems of the study is the evaluation of the influence of income levels on household savings habits. Another point of investigation is the relationship between education levels and propensity to save among households, and also the analysis of the effect of employment status on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. Determine the influence of income levels on household savings habits.
2. Investigate the relationship between education levels and propensity to save among households.
3. Analyze the effect of employment status on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study is analytical and descriptive. The design integrates both qualitative and quantitative methods to gain a holistic understanding of the subject matter. The quantitative aspect involves the collection and analysis of numerical data through a structured questionnaire distributed among a representative sample of the population. This approach will allow for statistical analysis and the identification of trends and patterns in household saving behavior. The qualitative component, although not the primary focus, will involve open-ended questions within the questionnaire to capture nuanced insights and personal experiences of the respondents. This mixed-methods approach ensures that the study not only quantifies the effectiveness of household saving behavior but also contextualizes the data within real-world experiences. The research will adopt a descriptive research design, which is appropriate for this type of empirical study. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon.

The study used a stratified random sampling method. This technique helps to represent differences in the population to get precise and reliable results. The population of the study is the households in Coimbatore, a city in Tamil Nadu due to its wider socio-economic demographics. The geographical scope of the study is limited to a specific region of Coimbatore to ensure that the findings are relevant and actionable. However, the insights gained from this study may have broader implications. The sample for this study will consist of 300 households from Coimbatore. Efforts will be made to ensure diversity within the sample, including a range of education, employment, and income. This diversity will help to capture a comprehensive picture of the various strategies and their effectiveness across different contexts. The sample size for this study is determined to be 300 households. This size is deemed sufficient to provide a robust dataset for statistical analysis while remaining manageable for data collection and analysis. The primary data for this study will be collected through a structured questionnaire.

The questionnaire will be designed to gather quantitative data. It will include a combination of closed-ended questions (e.g., Likert scale, multiple-choice) to facilitate statistical analysis, and open-ended questions to capture detailed insights and experiences. In addition to primary data, secondary data will be collected from various sources to provide context and support for the analysis. These sources will include academic journals, industry reports, case studies, and relevant literature on social media marketing in education. The secondary data will be used to compare and contrast the findings from the primary data, identify trends and best practices, and provide a theoretical framework for the study.

The data collected from the questionnaire was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software. The analysis will involve several statistical techniques to interpret the data and test the research hypotheses. Percent Analysis is a descriptive statistical method used to express data as percentages, which facilitates easier comparison and understanding of proportions within a dataset. It involves converting raw data into percentages of a whole, thereby highlighting the relative size of different components. This method is particularly useful in surveys, market research, and demographic studies, where it helps in illustrating the distribution and frequency of responses or characteristics. For example, in a survey analyzing job stress among female employees, percent analysis can show the proportion of respondents experiencing high, moderate, or low-stress levels, providing a clear and immediate visual representation of the data. Other tests such as One-way ANOVA, and the freedman test are applied to test the difference in the means scores and the difference in the preference of the respondents.

Ethical considerations are paramount in conducting research, especially when human participants are involved. The following measures will be taken to ensure the ethical integrity of the study. All participants will be provided with detailed information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Informed oral consent will be obtained from each participant before they take part in the study. Participants will have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The confidentiality of the participants will be strictly maintained. Personal information and responses will be anonymized to protect the identity of the respondents. Data will be stored securely and only accessible to the research team. Data collected during the study will be handled by data protection regulations. Electronic data will be encrypted, and physical data will be stored in a locked facility.

The data will be used solely for this research and will not be shared with third parties without the explicit consent of the participants. The research will be conducted with respect for the participants'

rights and dignity. Any questions or concerns raised by the participants during the study will be addressed promptly and appropriately. The research team ensures that the study does not cause any harm or discomfort to the participants. The research will be conducted with transparency and integrity. All findings will be reported honestly, and any limitations or potential biases will be acknowledged. The research process and results will be shared with the participants and other stakeholders, ensuring that the study contributes to the broader knowledge base and benefits the community.

ANALYSIS

The demographic profile of the respondents including the major details such as educational qualification, employment profile, and monthly household income which infer the household saving behaviors among the 300 respondents are analyzed in the first section of the analysis part. Then the One-Way ANOVA is used to identify whether there is any statistical difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income, and the difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save. Finally, the Friedman test is used to examine or evaluate the difference in the preference on the variables on allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The evaluation was below;

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Table 1. Education profile

		Frequency	Percent
Highest level of education	Primary education	40	13.3
	Secondary education	98	32.7
	Graduate level	76	25.3
	Postgraduate level	32	10.7
	Doctorate	54	18.0
	Total	300	100.0

The education of the respondents shows that the majority of the respondents completed secondary-level education (32.7%). Primary education is the highest qualification for 13.3% of the respondents, graduate level is for 76 respondents out of 300 respondents, 25.3% of the respondents have graduate level, 10.7% secured postgraduate qualification, and doctorate level education is for 18.0% of the respondents.

Table 2. Employment status

		Frequency	Percent
Current employment status	Employed full-time	93	31.0
	Employed part-time	40	13.3
	Self-employed	84	28.0
	Retired	29	9.7
	Others	54	18.0
	Total	300	100.0

Table 2 shows the employment profile of the respondents. Most of the respondents are employed full-time (31%), and 13.3% of the respondents are part-time employees. 28% of the respondents are employed or self-employed, 9.7% are retired from their jobs, and finally, 18% of the respondents belong to others.

Table 3. Monthly household income profile

		Frequency	Percent
Monthly household income	Less than 20000	40	13.3
	20,001-40,000	91	30.3
	40,001-60,000	86	28.7
	60,001-80,000	28	9.3
	More than 80,000	55	18.3
	Total	300	100.0

The monthly household income of the respondents reveals that the majority of the respondents earn 20,001-40,000 monthly (30.3%). 28.7% of the respondents are earning 40,001-60,000 incomes, more than 80,000 is the income of 18.3% of the total respondents, and less than 20000 is the monthly household income of 13.3% of the respondents. The small group (9.3%) of the respondents say that their income is between 60,001 to 80,000

INFLUENCE OF INCOME LEVELS ON HOUSEHOLD SAVINGS HABITS AND MONTHLY HOUSEHOLD INCOME

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income

H1: There is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income

Table 4. ANOVA on Influence of Income Levels on Household Savings Habits and monthly household income						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I save a fixed portion of my income every month.	Between Groups	230.490	4	57.622	50.865	.000
	Within Groups	334.190	295	1.133		
	Total	564.680	299			
Higher-income allows me to save more regularly.	Between Groups	223.149	4	55.787	50.185	.000
	Within Groups	327.931	295	1.112		
	Total	551.080	299			
My savings are affected by fluctuations in my income.	Between Groups	231.060	4	57.765	54.076	.000
	Within Groups	315.126	295	1.068		
	Total	546.187	299			
I prioritize saving regardless of my income level.	Between Groups	227.958	4	56.989	52.634	.000
	Within Groups	319.412	295	1.083		
	Total	547.370	299			
Income stability influences my saving behavior.	Between Groups	226.467	4	56.617	50.348	.000
	Within Groups	331.730	295	1.125		
	Total	558.197	299			
I find it difficult to save due to low income.	Between Groups	226.467	4	56.617	50.348	.000
	Within Groups	331.730	295	1.125		
	Total	558.197	299			
Unexpected income increases lead to increased savings.	Between Groups	223.931	4	55.983	50.506	.000
	Within Groups	326.986	295	1.108		
	Total	550.917	299			

I set saving goals based on my income.	Between Groups	201.798	4	50.449	44.410	.000
	Within Groups	335.119	295	1.136		
	Total	536.917	299			
My saving habits change with income changes.	Between Groups	214.722	4	53.681	48.036	.000
	Within Groups	329.664	295	1.118		
	Total	544.387	299			
High income motivates me to save more for the future.	Between Groups	204.489	4	51.122	45.993	.000
	Within Groups	327.898	295	1.112		
	Total	532.387	299			

The One-way ANOVA is used to check whether there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income. The result reveals that there is a significant difference in all variables such as saving a fixed portion of my income every month with a t value of 50.865, higher income allows me to save more regularly (50.185), savings are affected by fluctuations in my income (54.076), prioritize saving regardless of my income level (52.634), income stability influences my saving behavior (50.348), find it difficult to save due to low income (50.348), unexpected income increases lead to increased savings (50.506), set saving goals based on my income (44.410), saving habits change with income changes (48.036), and high income motivates me to save more for the future (45.993). The p-values for all variables are 0.000. It implies that the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5 percent level of significance. Hence, we can say that there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATION LEVELS AND PROPENSITY TO SAVE

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save

H1: There is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
My education has influenced my saving habits.	Between Groups	225.176	4	56.294	53.993	.000
	Within Groups	307.571	295	1.043		
	Total	532.747	299			
I am more likely to save because I am educated.	Between Groups	224.175	4	56.044	51.908	.000
	Within Groups	318.505	295	1.080		
	Total	542.680	299			
Education has taught me the importance of saving.	Between Groups	225.622	4	56.406	55.835	.000
	Within Groups	298.014	295	1.010		
	Total	523.637	299			
I save more effectively because of the financial literacy gained through education.	Between Groups	233.789	4	58.447	55.908	.000
	Within Groups	308.398	295	1.045		
	Total	542.187	299			
My saving behavior is a result of the financial knowledge acquired through education.	Between Groups	223.051	4	55.763	56.941	.000
	Within Groups	288.896	295	.979		
	Total	511.947	299			
Higher education levels lead to better saving habits.	Between Groups	210.257	4	52.564	51.837	.000
	Within Groups	299.139	295	1.014		
	Total	509.397	299			

Educated individuals are more likely to have saving plans.	Between Groups	214.988	4	53.747	54.990	.000
	Within Groups	288.332	295	.977		
	Total	503.320	299			
I understand the benefits of saving due to my education.	Between Groups	217.689	4	54.422	51.806	.000
	Within Groups	309.898	295	1.051		
	Total	527.587	299			
My education has helped me in making informed saving decisions.	Between Groups	225.488	4	56.372	53.743	.000
	Within Groups	309.429	295	1.049		
	Total	534.917	299			
Education has positively impacted my long-term saving goals.	Between Groups	230.966	4	57.742	55.160	.000
	Within Groups	308.804	295	1.047		
	Total	539.770	299			

The One-way ANOVA is used to check whether is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save. The result reveals that there is a significant difference in all variables such as education has influenced my saving habits, more likely to save because educated, education has taught me the importance of saving, saving more effectively because of the financial literacy gained through education, saving behavior is a result of the financial knowledge acquired through education, higher education levels lead to better saving habits, educated individuals are more likely to have saving plans, understand the benefits of saving due to my education, education has helped me in making informed saving decisions, education has positively impacted my long-term saving goals. The associate dt values are; 53.993, 51.908, 55.835, 55.908, 56.941, 51.837, 54.990, 51.806, 53.743, and 55.160. The p-values for all variables are 0.000. It implies that the hull hypothesis is rejected at a 5 percent level of significance. Hence, we can say that there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save.

ALLOCATION OF SAVINGS AMONG DIFFERENT INVESTMENT AVENUES

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference in the preference on the variables on allocation of savings among different investment avenues

H1: There is a significant difference in the preference for the variables on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues

	Mean Rank
Fixed Deposits	5.40
Mutual Funds	5.57
Real Estate	5.47
Stock Market Investments	5.23
Gold	5.37
Retirement Savings (e.g., EPF, PPF)	5.53
Insurance Policies	5.47
Savings Account	5.42
Cryptocurrency	5.73
Bonds	5.83

Table 6 shows the preference for the variables on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The result reveals the mean ranks are as follows; fixed deposits (5.40), mutual funds (5.57), real estate (5.47), stock market investments (5.23), gold (5.37), retirement savings (e.g., EPF, PPF) (5.53), insurance policies (5.47), savings account (5.42), cryptocurrency (5.73), and bonds (5.83). The lowest mean rank is for stock market investments (5.23). Therefore, the most preferred variable in the allocation of savings among different investment avenues is stock market investments.

N	300
Chi-Square	95.301
df	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 7 illustrates the test statistics results on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The total number of respondents is 300. The chi-square value is 95.301. The degrees of freedom are 9. The p-value (the sig value) is 0.000. The result shows that there is a difference in the preference for the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The result also supports the finding that the most preferred variable in the allocation of savings among different investment avenues is stock market investments.

FINDINGS

The education of the respondents shows that the majority of the respondents completed secondary-level education (32.7%). Primary education is the highest qualification for 13.3% of the respondents, graduate level is for 76 respondents out of 300 respondents, 25.3% of the respondents have graduate level, 10.7% secured postgraduate qualification, and doctorate level education is for 18.0% of the respondents. Most of the respondents are employed full-time (31%), and 13.3% of the respondents are part-time employees. 28% of the respondents are employed or self-employed, 9.7% are retired from their jobs, and finally, 18% of the respondents belong to others. The majority of the respondents earn 20,001-40,000 monthly as their total household income (30.3%). 28.7% of the respondents are earning 40,001-60,000 incomes, more than 80,000 is the income of 18.3% of the total respondents, and less than 20000 is the monthly household income of 13.3% of the respondents. The small group (9.3%) of the respondents say that their income is between 60,001 to 80,000

The One-way ANOVA is used to check whether there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income. The result reveals that there is a significant difference in all variables such as saving a fixed portion of my income every month, higher income allows me to save more regularly, savings are affected by fluctuations in my income, prioritize saving regardless of my income level, income stability influences my saving behavior, find it difficult to save due to low income, unexpected income increases lead to increased savings, set saving goals based on my income, saving habits change with income changes, and high income motivates me to save more for the future. The p-values for all variables are 0.000. It implies that the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5 percent level of significance. Hence, we can say that there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the influence of income levels on household savings habits and monthly household income.

The One-way ANOVA is used to check whether there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save. The result reveals that there is a significant difference in all variables such as education has influenced my saving

habits, more likely to save because educated, education has taught me the importance of saving, saving more effectively because of the financial literacy gained through education, saving behavior is a result of the financial knowledge acquired through education, higher education levels lead to better saving habits, educated individuals are more likely to have saving plans, understand the benefits of saving due to my education, education has helped me in making informed saving decisions, education has positively impacted my long-term saving goals. The p-values for all variables are 0.000. It implies that the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5 percent level of significance. Hence, we can say that there is a significant difference in the mean score on the variables on the relationship between education levels and propensity to save.

The Friedman test result reveals the mean ranks are as follows; fixed deposits, mutual funds, real estate, stock market investments, gold, retirement savings (e.g., EPF, PPF), insurance policies, savings accounts, cryptocurrency, and bonds. The lowest mean rank is for stock market investments. Therefore, the most preferred variable in the allocation of savings among different investment avenues is stock market investments. The test statistics results on the allocation of savings among different investment avenues reveal that the chi-square value is 95.301, and the p-value (the sig value) of 0.000. The result shows that there is a difference in the preference for the allocation of savings among different investment avenues. The result also supports the finding that the most preferred variable in the allocation of savings among different investment avenues is stock market investments.

IMPLICATIONS

By examining the impact of socio-economic factors on household savings behavior, this research seeks to provide actionable insights and strategic recommendations for optimizing savings habits. The relationship between demographic variables with savings patterns is a multifaceted and dynamic field of study. By harnessing the savings strategically, households can not only increase savings but also foster deeper connections with demographics representing socio-economic status, ultimately driving growth, and sustained success in the competitive world for the better future. The study offers understanding and informs to the households, and enhances the further research to the academicians, practitioners, and researchers for inculcating the savings patterns among the households.

FUTURE RESEARCH

- Sample Size and Demographics: The 300 respondents in the survey may have limited how far the results can be applied. The results may be skewed by the demographic profile.
- Self-Reported Data: Relying too much on self-reported information obtained from questionnaires might lead to biases including social desirability bias and erroneous self-evaluation.
- More and More Diverse Samples: To improve the generalizability of the results across various demographic groups, future research should strive to use more and more varied samples.
- Cross-Cultural Studies: Examining how household savings are impacted by socio-economic factors in various cultural contexts might provide insightfully

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